

SCIENCE TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICES AND ATTRIBUTES: AN EVALUATION

Cherryl A. Largo, Charmaine G. Rubio, Myrna Josefa S. Aldeon, Dino C. Mondarte

Graduate School, St. Paul University Dumaguete, Dumaguete City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15331820>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the performance of science teachers in terms of their professional knowledge, professional practices and professional attributes using standard-based rubrics of the “Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education” (FSTE). With the use of survey, the numerical data were analyzed and qualitative responses were done through Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and classroom observations. A total of 37 science teachers; 11 school principals; and 321 students from Science High Schools of Negros Oriental who took part in the study. Findings revealed that administrators rated science teachers as “master science teachers” in terms of professional knowledge and practices and as “certified science mentor” in their professional attributes. On the other hand, teachers had “very satisfactory” performance in terms of professional knowledge, practices and attributes as rated by their students. The available evidence suggests that science teachers demonstrate high level performance in terms of their professional knowledge, practices and attributes, however, some of these elements in each of the areas need to be improved. As an output, an Individual Development Plan (IDP) to improve teachers work performance was designed.

Keywords: *Professional knowledge, Practices, Attributes*

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century teaching, it is expected that teachers are equipped with complex skills to match with students needs and competencies such as deep mastery,

critical thinking, complex problem solving, effective communication and collaboration, and self-direction (SEI-DOST & UP NISMED, 2011).

Teacher qualities have been the most powerful tool in the teaching and learning processes. Moreover, these so-called qualities are linked with the students' performance in national achievement tests which serve as the cutting-edge of education. Professional development among teachers have been a national strategy in order to help teachers and identify their professional development needs that are not working well.

Effective teaching in science education includes developing the students' skills in an inquiry method and involves students to engage in real-life experience towards becoming informed decision makers in the community. UNESCO considered teachers as dominant forces for ensuring quality in education and are key to achieving sustainable global progress (Murray, 2021). They play a pivotal role in shaping a better society (Ansari & Malik, 2013). Therefore, science teachers not only educate their students but also contribute to a more informed, innovative and responsible society.

However, with the current problem science education in the Philippine is facing, our nation needs to strategize ways to address and improve the quality of teaching through their professional knowledge, practices, and attributes. Consequently, this study seeks to find out the level of performance of science teachers in terms of mastery of subject matter, practices and their professional attributes. All these are anchored on the objective of raising the quality of science education.

As an output of this study, the researcher designed a professional development plan for individual teachers known as IDP to improve teachers work performance; develop and enhance the knowledge, skills and change their instructional practices in ways that support student learning and address students learning challenges.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the performance of science teachers in terms of professional knowledge, professional practice and professional attributes. Specifically, the study is designed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the school administrator's rating of the science teachers' level of performance using the standard-based rubrics from the Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) in terms of:
 - 1.1 professional knowledge;
 - 1.2 professional practices; and
 - 1.3 professional attitudes?
2. What is the science teachers' self- rating as regards their performance using the standard-based rubrics from the Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) in terms of:
 - 2.1 professional knowledge
 - 2.2 professional practices; and
 - 2.3 professional attitudes?

3. What is the students' rating as regards the level of performance of their science teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1 professional knowledge;
 - 3.2 professional practices; and
 - 3.3 professional attributes?
4. What is the school administrator's rating of the science teachers' level of performance using the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) evaluation tool for teachers in terms of:
 - 4.1 professional knowledge;
 - 4.2 professional practice; and
 - 4.3 professional attributes?
5. What is the relationship between the teachers' rating using the standard-based rubrics from Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) and students' rating on the level of performance of science teachers in terms of:
 - 5.1 professional knowledge;
 - 5.2 professional practice; and
 - 5.3 professional attributes?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a mixed research design- qualitative and quantitative. The questionnaire was administered through survey to yield quantitative data that would describe the level of performance of science teachers using standard-based rubrics based on the Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) and describing respondents as a neophyte science teacher, an emerging professional science teacher, a master science teacher, or a certified science mentor. This study also utilized Focus Group Discussion (FGD) to discuss and validate answers in the survey. The data gathered from FGD and classroom observation were utilized as qualitative.

The study was conducted in the secondary public Science High Schools of Negros Oriental. For this study, all secondary science teachers from grade seven to grade twelve of the secondary public science high schools of Negros Oriental were the respondents. Demographic characteristics of the teachers in this study were included. All the secondary school principals and assistant principals of the school were also included in the study. Researcher used the sample size taken from the population of students currently enrolled in grade ten or grade twelve for the School Year 2019-2020 of the mentioned schools who are currently taking up science subjects. One section per science school was taken as student respondents.

Research Instruments

Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE)

The instrument used in this study was a standard- based rubrics to evaluate the performance of Science teachers as describe in the Framework for Philippine Science

Teacher Education (FSTE). It attempts to capture the nature of professional development required to develop effective science teachers. The rubrics contain both a numerical value and a qualitative description. FSTE is the product of the collaborative efforts of DOST-Science Education Institute (DOST-SEI) and University of the Philippines National Institute of Science and Mathematics Education Development (UP NISMED-DOST, 2010).

Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)

IPCRF is an assessment tool for government employees to rate the task a teacher accomplished for a year. Documents were obtained from the principal’s office. IPCRF is composed of the KRA’s which involves Instructional Competence, Professional growth, Learning Outcomes, Community Involvement and the Special Task. The teacher’s level of performance is rated using a 5-point scale: 5-outstanding, 4-very satisfactory, 3-satisfactory, 2-unsatisfactory and 1-poor.

Student Questionnaire

A student questionnaire was made to rate the level of performance of their science teachers and was presented to the researcher’s adviser, dean other experts for improvement and ensure sufficiency. The questionnaire can be answered using the scale: 4-always, 3- sometimes, 2-rarely, and 1-never. It was piloted to grade 10 students. In determining the reliability of the student questionnaire, Cronbachs alpha was used. The results of the reliability test were as follows: professional knowledge has Cronbachs coefficient alpha $\alpha=0.7$, fair reliability, while both professional practices and attributes has $\alpha=0.84$, it means both areas have very good reliability.

RESULTS

1.School Administrators’ Rating of the Science Teachers’ level of performance using the FSTE in terms of Professional Knowledge, Practices and Attributes

Table 1.1

Administrator’s Ratings of the Science Teachers in terms of Professional Knowledge

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F			
Parameters	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	CM	VD
Knowledge of Science content, their connections and application	2.33	0.82	3.00	NA	2.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.06	MST

Pedagogical Content Knowledge	3.00	0.63	3.00	NA	2.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.17	MST
Curricular Knowledge	2.67	0.82	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.00	NA	3.11	MST
CM	2.67	0.70	3.00	0.00	2.33	0.58	3.00	0.00	4.00	0.00	3.67	0.58		
Grade Mean													3.17	MST

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description; MST- Master Science Teacher
Scale: 1.00-1.75 Neophyte Science Teacher 1.76-2.50 Emerging Professional Science Teacher 2.51-3.25 Master Science Teacher 3.26-4.00 Certified Science Mentor

Table 1.2
Administrator’s Ratings of the Science Teachers in terms of Professional Practice

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F			
Parameters	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	WM	SD	CM	VD
P1: Designing sound Science teaching & learning programs suitable for varied learners	2.67	0.82	3.00	NA	2.95	MST								
P2: Creating & maintaining a learner-centered emotionally supportive, & safe learning	2.50	0.55	3.00	NA	2.92	MST								
P3: Engaging students in scientific investigations to generate construct, test knowledge, & evaluate evidence	2.67	0.52	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	2.00	NA	2.95	MST
P4: Finding & implementing ways to extend	2.67	0.52	3.00	NA	2.00	NA	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	2.00	NA	2.58	MST

student's
knowledge &
skills

P5: Building student's confidence & capacity to use scientific processes to make informed decisions	2.50	0.55	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	2.00	NA	3.14	MST
P6: Monitoring & assessing student's learning	2.83	0.41	3.00	NA	2.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.31	CSM
CM	2.64	0.32	3.00	0.00	2.67	0.52	3.33	0.52	3.50	0.55	2.67	0.82		

Grand Mean **2.98 MST**

*Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description; MST- Master Science Teacher; CSM-Certified Science Mentor
Scale: 1.00-1.75 Neophyte Science Teacher 1.76-2.50 Emerging Professional Science Teacher 2.51-3.25 Master Science Teacher 3.26-4.00 Certified Science Mentor*

Table 1.3
Administrator's Ratings of the Science Teachers in terms of Professional Attributes

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F			
Parameters	WM	SD	CM	VD										
Being a reflective and critical thinker	2.27	0.82	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	3.11	MST
Being a lifelong learner	2.83	0.41	3.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.31	CSM
Being a Member of a community of learners	2.67	0.82	3.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	4.00	NA	3.61	CSM
CM	2.72	0.57	3.00	0.00	3.33	0.58	4.00	0.00	3.33	0.58	3.67	0.58		
Grand Mean														3.34 CSM

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description; MST- Master Science Teacher; CSM-Certified Science Mentor

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Neophyte Science Teacher 1.76-2.50 Emerging Professional Science Teacher 2.51-3.25 Master Science Teacher 3.26-4.00 Certified Science Mentor

2.Science Teachers' Self Rating of their Performance using the Standard-Based Rubrics from the Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) in terms of: Professional Knowledge, Professional Practices and Professional Attributes

Table 2.1
Teachers' Self Rating in terms of Professional Knowledge

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F				
Parameters	WM	SD	CM	VD											
Knowledge of Science content, their connections and application	2.38	0.81	2.86	1.07	2.00	0.00	3.00	1.41	2.83	0.75	2.00	0.82	2.51	MST	
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	2.81	0.83	2.86	0.90	3.00	0.00	3.50	0.71	2.83	0.98	2.59	0.58	2.92	MST	
Curricular Knowledge	3.00	0.82	2.86	0.69	3.00	0.00	3.50	0.71	3.00	0.89	2.50	0.58	2.98	MST	
CM	2.73	0.67	2.86	0.74	3.00	0.00	3.3	0.94	2.89	0.78	2.33	0.47			
Grade Mean														2.80	MST

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description; MST- Master Science Teacher

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Neophyte Science Teacher 1.76-2.50 Emerging Professional Science Teacher 2.51-3.25 Master Science Teacher 3.26-4.00 Certified Science Mentor

Table 2.2
Teacher's Self-Rating in terms of Professional Practice

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F			
Parameters	WM	SD	CM	VD										
P1:Designing sound Science	2.50	0.63	2.71	0.95	2.50	0.71	3.00	1.41	2.83	0.75	2.75	0.96	2.72	MST

teaching &
learning
programs
suitable for
varied
learners

P2:Creating & maintaining a learner-centered, emotionally supportive, & safe learning 2.75 1.00 2.85 1.07 3.50 0.71 3.50 0.71 2.33 0.82 2.75 0.96 2.95 MST

P3:Engaging students in scientific investigations to generate construct test knowledge & evaluate evidence 2.75 0.77 2.57 0.79 3.50 0.70 3.00 0.00 2.67 1.03 2.50 0.58 2.67 MST

P4:Finding & implementing ways to extend student's knowledge & skills 2.75 0.77 2.86 0.90 3.50 0.71 3.50 0.71 2.67 1.03 2.75 0.96 3.01 MST

P5:Building students' confidence & capacity to use scientific processes to make informed decisions 2.81 0.75 2.86 1.07 3.50 0.71 2.50 0.71 2.67 1.03 3.25 0.96 2.93 MST

P6:Monitoring & assessing students' learning 2.88 0.72 2.71 0.95 3.50 0.71 3.50 0.71 2.67 0.52 3.00 0.82 3.04MST

CM 2.74 0.59 2.71 0.81 3.17 0.23 3.17 0.47 2.64 0.74 2.83 0.83

Grand Mean **2.89 MST**

Table 2.3
Teacher's Self Rating in terms of Professional Attributes

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F		CM	VD
	WM	SD												
Being a reflective & critical thinker	2.88	0.89	2.86	0.69	2.50	0.71	3.00	0.00	2.33	1.03	2.50	0.58	2.68	MST
Being a lifelong learner	3.19	0.54	2.86	0.69	3.50	0.00	3.00	0.00	2.83	0.98	2.75	0.50	2.94	MST
Being a member of a community of learners	3.00	0.89	2.71	0.95	2.50	0.71	3.00	0.00	2.83	0.96	2.25	1.26	2.72	CSM
CM	3.02	0.55	2.81	0.60	2.67	0.00	3.00	0.00	2.67	0.82	2.50	0.69		
Grand Mean													2.78	MST

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal descriptio
MST- Master Science Teacher; CSM-Certified Science Mentor

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Neophyte Science Teacher 1.76-2.50 Emerging Professional Science Teacher
2.51-3.25 Master Science Teacher 3.26-4.00 Certified Science Mentor

3. Students' Rating of the Level of Performance of Their Science Teachers
A. Students' Rating in terms of Professional Knowledge

Table 3.1
Students' Rating in terms of professional knowledge

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F		CM	VD
	WM	SD												
1.explain science lessons clearly and communicates well	3.61	0.51	3.81	0.80	3.73	0.52	3.38	0.49	3.81	0.40	3.93	0.26	3.71	VS
2. clarify our understanding of scientific concepts and misconceptions in textbooks	3.43	0.60	3.67	0.48	3.57	0.63	3.38	0.68	3.71	0.46	3.55	0.51	3.56	VS
3.give directions	3.69	0.50	3.89	0.32	3.70	0.47	3.48	0.51	3.84	0.37	3.83	0.38	3.74	VS

and explain what is expected on tasks

4.respond clearly and concisely to questions asked in class 3.56 0.58 3.64 0.49 3.73 0.45 3.41 0.63 3.68 0.48 3.59 0.57 3.60 VS

5.gives questions and problems that allow us to think analytically and critically 3.55 0.60 3.44 0.50 3.47 0.51 3.24 0.69 3.35 0.61 3.69 0.47 3.46 VS

6.challenges us to justify our thinking, to explain, demonstrate & use our ideas learned 3.57 0.58 3.44 0.50 3.50 0.57 3.48 0.51 3.35 0.61 3.66 0.55 3.50 VS

7.provide an alternative explanations or additional examples when we are confused 3.57 0.65 3.64 0.49 3.73 0.45 3.59 0.50 3.55 0.57 3.48 0.57 3.60 VS

8. relate classroom content/lesson to the laboratory content, activities and experiments 3.47 0.64 3.58 0.55 3.53 0.63 3.14 0.64 3.48 0.63 3.55 0.51 3.46 VS

9. relates Science lessons to previous and future learning 3.65 0.59 3.61 0.49 3.60 0.50 3.45 0.51 3.61 0.56 3.69 0.60 3.60 VS

10. relates lessons to complex issues and big ideas that provide deeper meaning to give us better understanding of the content/lesson 3.43 0.63 3.58 0.50 3.50 0.63 3.48 0.63 3.45 0.68 3.55 0.51 3.50 VS

11. provide 3.28 0.69 3.36 0.49 3.43 0.57 3.21 0.68 3.29 0.53 3.55 0.63 3.35 VS

scientific investigations and analysis of data obtained from activities and experiments

12. help us see connections/relationships between science, technology, society and across other disciplines 3.54 0.68 3.53 0.51 3.50 0.51 3.38 0.56 3.45 0.62 3.59 0.50 3.50 VS

connections/relationships between science, technology, society and across other disciplines

13.engage us in exploration, inquiry and discovery through experiments, problem solving, field trips & demonstration to deepen understanding of the lesson 3.34 0.77 3.28 0.45 3.40 0.62 3.21 0.73 3.19 0.60 3.48 0.57 3.32 VS

engage us in exploration, inquiry and discovery through experiments, problem solving, field trips & demonstration to deepen understanding of the lesson

14.uses variety of science activities (e.g. groupwork, drill,games, fieldwork, think-pair share, use of equipment, tools, technology and worksheets) to make lesson meaningful 3.54 0.61 3.86 0.35 3.40 0.62 3.52 0.57 3.84 0.37 3.79 0.41 3.66 VS

uses variety of science activities (e.g. groupwork, drill,games, fieldwork, think-pair share, use of equipment, tools, technology and worksheets) to make lesson meaningful

CM 3.52 0.38 3.60 0.23 3.56 0.34 **3.38** 0.30 3.54 0.28 **3.64** 0.28 3.54 VS

Grand Mean 3.54 VS

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description;

VS-Very satisfactory, S-satisfactory, U-Unsatisfactory, P-Poor

Scale: 1.00-1.75 Poor 1.76-2.50 Unsatisfactory

2.51-3.25Satisfactory 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfactory

Table 3.2
Students' Rating in terms of Professional Practices

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F		CM	VD
	WM	SD												
1. engages us in various activities individually or in groups (e.g.projects, experiments, investigations etc) and share findings/ results	3.73	0.50	3.61	0.49	3.73	0.45	3.62	0.49	3.77	0.43	3.79	0.41	3.71	VS
2. engage us in making our own scientific research and investigations (e.g. investigatory project) and share with others	3.17	0.90	3.75	0.44	3.67	0.55	3.55	0.63	3.65	0.55	3.48	0.57	3.55	VS
3.engage us in discussions and encourage us to critique on articles and reports about science and follow TV programs on new advances in science	3.17	0.73	3.14	0.35	3.10	0.66	2.93	0.46	2.81	0.75	3.21	0.68	3.06	S
4.use effective materials (e.g. calculators, computer, CD-ROMS, films, videos, audio visual aids, and laboratory simulations) in science discussion	3.67	0.52	3.50	0.51	3.40	0.72	3.14	0.58	3.35	0.66	3.62	0.56	3.45	VS
5.use real-life examples to make science	3.57	0.60	3.64	0.49	3.73	0.45	3.41	0.68	3.32	0.70	3.38	0.68	3.51	VS

learning more meaningful and connect with our personal experiences

6.provides us additional materials/resources (e.g.handouts, worksheets, manuals) apart from textbooks to enhance learning 3.52 0.63 3.19 0.47 3.43 0.68 2.97 0.57 3.16 0.73 3.48 0.51 3.29 VS

7.pays careful attention to the knowledge, skills, attitudes and beliefs that we bring to the science classroom 3.57 0.53 3.36 0.49 3.67 0.48 3.31 0.54 3.58 0.67 3.66 0.48 3.53 VS

8.helps us to express our ideas, use science language and communicate it to different audiences (e.g. debates, contests, competitions, etc) 3.22 0.77 3.08 0.44 3.43 0.57 2.93 0.53 3.06 0.81 3.55 0.51 3.21 S

9. available to students outside class time for tutoring, review work, or to answer questions 3.01 0.81 3.11 0.40 3.40 0.50 2.76 0.79 2.84 0.86 3.07 0.88 3.03 S

10. control disruptive behavior in class /manages misbehavior 3.60 0.58 3.61 0.55 3.57 0.50 3.59 0.57 3.68 0.60 3.76 0.51 3.64 VS

11. ensure that all voices are heard in the discussion 3.56 0.62 3.36 0.49 3.80 0.41 3.28 0.88 3.58 0.81 3.76 0.44 3.56 VS

12. use class time in an efficient and productive manner	3.41	0.76	3.17	0.56	3.90	0.31	3.31	0.47	3.55	0.62	3.48	0.51	3.47	VS
13. establishes a warm and supportive relationship with us building on respect & cooperation	3.36	0.63	3.50	0.65	3.87	0.35	3.59	0.57	3.81	0.48	3.79	0.41	3.67	VS
14. offers encouragement and positive reinforcement (e.g. rewards, giving extra points) as well as constructive criticism	3.42	0.74	3.31	0.58	3.67	0.55	3.24	0.64	3.58	0.50	3.62	0.49	3.47	VS
15. provides guided and independent practice such as assignments, seatworks, quizzes etc.	3.74	0.47	3.56	0.56	3.67	0.55	3.52	0.57	3.71	0.53	3.59	0.50	3.63	VS
16. tests and assignments are corrected and returned in a timely manner	3.58	0.52	3.42	0.50	3.80	0.41	3.38	0.49	3.71	0.46	3.52	0.51	3.57	VS
17. use criteria/ standards (e.g. rubrics, checklist, reflection) to self-monitor, reflect and evaluate our own work, performance and progress	3.57	0.64	3.36	0.54	3.60	0.50	3.21	0.62	3.55	0.62	3.83	0.47	3.52	VS
18. provide written feedback on us	3.24	0.76	3.25	0.55	3.27	0.64	3.14	0.69	2.90	0.87	3.41	0.63	3.20	VS

(e.g. our strengths and weaknesses) in addition to our mark or grade) for improvement

19. provide immediate feedback (during and after) when we are working on particular tasks, experiment or activity 3.47 0.64 3.53 0.56 3.60 0.62 3.52 0.57 3.26 0.82 3.55 0.51 3.49 VS

20. read & comment on the reflections we have written (e.g. in the journals) 3.23 0.85 3.44 0.61 3.40 0.56 3.28 0.70 2.74 0.73 3.52 0.51 3.27 VS

CM 3.45 0.37 3.39 0.26 3.59 0.28 3.28 0.33 3.38 0.38 3.55 0.28 3.45VS

Grand Mean **3.44 VS**

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description
VS-Very satisfactory, S-satisfactory, U-Unsatisfactory, P-Poor
Scale: 1.00-1.75 Poor 1.76-2.50 Unsatisfactory
2.51-3.25 Satisfactory 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfactory

Table 3.3
Students' Rating in terms of Professional Attributes

DIVISIONS	Division A		Division B		Division C		Division D		Division E		Division F		CM	VD
	WM	SD												
1.actively supports and participates in science programs, workshops, trainings and seminars in school	3.76	0.51	3.78	0.42	3.90	0.31	3.55	0.51	3.58	0.62	3.83	0.38	3.73	VS

2. an active member of different science organizations (eg. science club of students/ and or professional teachers)	3.35	0.77	3.72	0.45	3.73	0.45	3.45	0.57	3.00	0.93	3.76	0.51	3.50VS
3. participates in research projects and contests in and outside of the school (e.g. science projects, scientific discoveries, science fair, exhibits)	3.59	0.72	3.61	0.49	3.77	0.43	3.24	0.51	3.58	0.56	3.83	0.38	3.60VS
4. seeks resources from outside schools (e.g. learning materials, equipment, tools, ICT, etc) to be use in class	3.33	0.83	3.44	0.50	3.57	0.57	2.97	0.63	3.13	0.88	3.55	0.51	3.33VS
5. conducts his/her own research on science and shares the results with others and receive recognition/ awards for work done	3.18	0.77	3.33	0.48	3.30	0.53	2.86	0.44	3.19	0.83	3.38	0.62	3.21 S
6. contribute in developing science programs, activities and organizations for school improvement	3.38	0.78	3.61	0.49	3.70	0.47	3.14	0.64	3.29	0.74	3.45	0.57	3.41VS

through
collaboration
on tasks by
leading
as chairman/
coordinator of
an activity/event

7.regularly collect and gather information about problems that students may have in learning science (e.g. materials used, lack or resources, lessons,etc) 3.37 0.72 3.39 0.49 3.57 0.57 3.03 0.57 3.42 0.67 3.34 0.61 3.35 VS

8.gives talks and serves as resource person or trainer in programs, seminars, trainings of the school and to the community 3.18 0.81 3.53 0.56 3.40 0.67 3.14 0.69 3.29 3.41 0.68 0.68 3.21 S

9.communicates with students, parents, and other personnel appropriately to establish relationship 3.36 0.79 3.56 0.50 3.63 0.49 3.31 0.66 3.58 0.62 3.59 0.57 3.51 S

10. works collaboratively with other teachers within the school to provide the needs of the school and students 3.51 0.64 3.61 0.49 3.67 0.55 3.45 0.51 3.52 0.68 3.83 0.38 3.60 VS

11. joins community 3.27 0.79 3.36 0.59 3.57 0.50 3.17 0.60 3.23 0.67 3.62 0.49 3.37 VS

organizations
or network
to remain
up to date
on issues and
developments
in science
education

CM 3.38 0.59 3.54 0.30 **3.62** 0.29 3.21 0.37 **3.35** 0.50 3.60 0.31

Grand Mean **3.44 VS**

Legend: WM-weighted mean; SD-standard deviation; CM-composite mean; VD-verbal description; VS-Very satisfactory, S-satisfactory, U-Unsatisfactory, P-Poor

*Scale: 1.00-1.75 Poor 1.77-2.50 Unsatisfactory
2.51-3.25 Satisfactory 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfactory*

4.School Administrators' Rating of the Science Teachers' Level of Performance using the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) evaluation tool for Teachers in terms of Professional Knowledge, Professional Practice and Professional Attributes

Table 4.1
Administrators' Ratings in terms of Professional Knowledge using IPCRF

DIVISION	Division A	Division B	Division C	Division D	Division E	Division F	GRAND MEAN:
WM	4.05	4.40	4.71	4.38	4.32	4.52	4.40
VD	VS	VS	O	VS	VS	O	VS

*Scale: 4.500-5.000 Outstanding 3.500-4.499 Very Satisfactory 2.500-3.499 Satisfactory
1.500-2.499 Unsatisfactory below 1.499 Poor*

Table 4.2
Administrators' Ratings in terms of Professional Practices using IPCRF

DIVISION	Division A	Division B	Division C	Division D	Division E	Division F	GRAND MEAN
WM	4.18	4.35	4.36	4.57	4.45	4.68	4.43
VD	VS	VS	VS	O	VS	O	VS

*Scale: 4.500-5.000 Outstanding 3.500-4.499 Very Satisfactory 2.500-3.499 Satisfactory
1.500-2.499 Unsatisfactory below 1.499 Poor*

Table 4.3*Administrators' Ratings in terms of Professional Attributes using IPCRF*

DIVISION	Division A	Division B	Division C	Division D	Division E	Division F	GRAND MEAN
WM	4.57	4.29	5.00	3.75	4.67	5.00	4.55
VD	O	VS	O	VS	O	O	O

Scale: 4.500-5.000 Outstanding
1.500-2.499 Unsatisfactory

3.500-4.499 Very Satisfactory
below 1.499 Poor

2.500-3.499 Satisfactory

5. Relationship between the Teachers' Rating and Students' Rating on the Level of Performance of Science Teachers in terms of: Professional Knowledge; Professional Practice; and Professional Attributes

Table 5.1*Relationship between the teachers' rating and students' rating*

Parameter	R value	Description	Significant Level Alpha =0.05	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	0.88	High Correlation	0.02	Reject the Null Hypothesis	There is significant high correlation
Practices	0.08	Weak to No Correlation	0.88	Fail to Reject the Null Hypothesis	There is no significant correlation.
Attributes	0.7	Moderately Correlation	0.12	Reject the Null Hypothesis	There is a moderately correlation. However, the relationship is not significant

DISCUSSION

School administrators' ratings of the science teachers' level of performance using the FSTE in terms of professional knowledge, practices and attitudes were as follows: for professional knowledge- master level with the grand mean of 3.17; for professional practice- master science teacher with a grand mean of 2.98; and for professional attributes certified science mentor with a grand mean of 3.34. The results imply that science teachers consistently demonstrate a high level of performance in the area of

professional attributes. Teachers' contributions to their science workforce/ community were marked excellent because they were rated "certified science mentor" by their principals. Professional knowledge of teachers is related to their overall competencies and standards established for teacher education in particular. (Liakopoulou, 2011).

Science teacher's self-rating of their performance using the standard-based rubrics from the Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) were as follows: for professional knowledge--master science teacher with a grand mean of 2.80; for professional practices-- master science teacher in all six parameters with a grand mean of 2.89; and for professional attributes is master science teacher in all three parameters with a grand mean of 2.78. This all implies that science teachers are effective teachers and they have strong subject matter expertise, effective teaching skills, and positive qualities that contribute to successful student learning. Mishra & Koehler (2006) assert that teachers who have strong grasp of their subject matter find different ways to represent it and making it more accessible for students.

Students rating on the level of performance of their science teachers were as follows: for professional knowledge very satisfactory, with a grand mean of 3.45 which implies that their science teachers demonstrate a high level of performance in terms of professional knowledge, that their science teachers are proficient in their fields, possess expertise in the subject matter they taught and have substantial expertise in science. There are areas of knowledge that are essential prerequisites for all teachers, which make up the core of professional knowledge (Meijer et al., 2001). For professional practices very satisfactory with a grand mean of 3.44. These results imply that their science teachers always demonstrate capability in maintaining a learner-centered supportive learning environment, engaging them in scientific activities that enhance their learning and abilities; and for professional attributes very satisfactory with a grand mean of 3.44. This implies that science teachers are always or consistently demonstrate a high level of performance in terms of their professional attributes. Science teachers work collaboratively with students and community in supporting and improving their learner development and achievement. The engagement of students and an emphasis on lifelong learning for both learners and teachers can drive improvements in the quality of education (Peng et al., 2014).

School administrators' rating of the science teachers' level of performance using the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) evaluation tool were as follows: for the professional knowledge very satisfactory with a grand mean of 4.40; for professional practices very satisfactory with a grand mean of 4.43 and for professional attributes— outstanding with a grand mean of 4.55. This implies that teacher who are outstanding facilitate learning using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies and classroom management practices and address learner diversity, thus, improve motivation and interest of students that will result to increase scores in NAT of the students. The essential qualities of an effective teacher are vital because teachers' play a crucial role in the classroom, significantly influencing students' learning outcomes (Sahin & Adiguzel, 2014).

The relationship between the teachers' rating using the standard-based rubrics from Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education (FSTE) and students' rating were as follows: There is a high correlation between teachers' rating and students' rating in terms of professional knowledge with r value of 0.88. The numerical results then, imply that in the area of professional knowledge, students' ratings and the self-performance ratings of the teachers are highly the same. They strongly agree that their teachers really master their lessons and display high regard on the content of the subject matter they are teaching. However, there is no significant relationship between teachers and students' responses in terms of professional practices with r value of 0.08. This implies that in the area of professional practice, students' ratings did not seem to agree on the self-rating of their teachers. Teachers might have rated themselves higher compared to the ratings of their students. The students answered the questionnaire sometimes to rarely and supported it during the FGD that their teachers lack in knowledge, teaching strategies and methods appropriate for science teaching. Many science teachers turn to lecturing instead of providing students with engaging and challenging activities that enable the students to develop creative ideas. Oftentimes, science teaching is still textbook-based and, more often than not, concepts are not relevant to the daily life or the community. According to many students, "science is boring and irrelevant". Small group activities were performed by students but many teachers did not adequately process the results of these activities. The three questions where students answered satisfactorily in the questionnaire and the reasons of teachers and students disagreements in their answers: (1) engage students in discussions and encourage them to critique on articles and reports about science and follow TV programs on new advances in science (2) helps us to express our ideas, use science language and communicate it to different audiences (e.g. debates, contests, competitions, etc); and (3) available to students outside class time for tutoring, review work, or to answer questions.

There is a moderate correlation between teachers' rating and students' rating in terms of professional attributes with r value of 0.7. However, the relationship is not significant. This means that both responses from both respondents are not related. As to professional attributes, although the relationship is moderate between the ratings of the students and the self-ratings of the teachers, both respondents agree that there are truths on the self-ratings of the teachers. Students agree that teachers actively support and participate in science programs, workshops, trainings and seminars in school as active member of different science organizations (e.g. science club of students and/or professional teachers); teachers participate in research projects and contests in and outside of the school (e.g. science projects, scientific discoveries, science fair, exhibits); teachers work collaboratively with other teachers within the school to provide the needs of the school and students for improvement; teachers contribute in developing science programs, activities and organizations for school improvement through collaboration on tasks by leading as chairman/coordinator of an activity/event; teachers join community organizations or network to remain up to date on issues and developments in science education and science teachers communicate with students, parents, and other personnel appropriately to establish relationship. It can be concluded that becoming an effective teacher is a challenging endeavor, it is a multifaceted process that extends beyond

immediate success but encompasses appropriate values and pursuit of long-term achievements (Rubio, 2009).

Conclusions

The findings of the study give light to the statement of the following conclusions. Generally, science teachers in Science High Schools of the six (6) divisions are qualified to teach in Science High Schools. They have long years of teaching experience in their own field and have taught multiple grade levels, however, these are not sufficient to guarantee an effective science teacher. In conclusion, science teachers exhibit in-depth knowledge and teaching skills fitted for science teaching, however, not all science teachers in the Science High Schools of the six divisions perform effectively and efficiently in terms of professional practices. Science teachers demonstrate high level of performance in terms of professional knowledge, practices and attributes, however, some of these elements in each of the areas need to be improved. Science teachers are proficient in their fields, but despite the commendable results in the survey, the FGD gives a significant implication that teachers are not yet fully equipped with complex skills to match with students needs and competencies. Science teachers have applied mastery of content knowledge, facilitated learning appropriately and address learner diversity, thus, improve motivation and interest of students. However, these does not always corroborate with some school divisions since their students do not perform well in the National Achievement Test. Responses differ from teachers and students in terms of professional practices. This is to note that the teachers in this area need to improve on certain elements in their teaching such as in the content and pedagogical skills suitable for science teaching. It is also concluded that teachers lack the involvement of parents in the academic affairs of their children.

Recommendations

Science teachers should aim for advancement for themselves by enrolling in further studies such as taking graduate and post-graduate degrees specifically in science teaching or other related fields. Division supervisors and school administrators and relevant leaders should create, evaluate, and revise policies and practices that encourage teachers to engage more in professional learning related to science especially on teaching practices and structure time to allow collaboration. Develop internal capacity in science while seeking external partners with science expertise. Science teachers should employ self-assessment on their specific professional needs in terms of knowledge, practices and attributes aligned with FSTE. Thus, designing an Individual Development Plan is strongly recommended to clarify areas that need improvement towards becoming effective science teachers. Science teachers should explore on other teaching ideas to explain important concepts to students. Science lessons should be presented through the use of varied activities and appropriate learning materials to aid students' learning, thus, relevant trainings should be conducted. There is also a need for the teachers to strengthen their relationship and collaboration with parents through regular meetings and dialogues as possible feedback mechanism. These should also be included in their Individual Development Plan as part of the tangible activities. The divisions administrators

and curriculum leaders should painstakingly look into the content and skills being taught in the classroom and tested in the achievement test to ensure consistency and equivalence. The science teachers in particular should have the individual development plan (IDP) for every indicator of the IPCRF. This is to enhance their practices, knowledge and in order to meet the highest standards on certain indicators. The IDP should contain the KRA, objectives, learning and development needs, current proficiency, target proficiency, development opportunity, projects, target date, resources and success indicator. Document implementation of this plan. The school administrators, teachers, students, parents and other stakeholders should actively involve themselves in the planning of the teachers' professional development plan through the results of constant evaluation of teachers' performance both from self and peers. The IDP should serve as concrete vehicle in the translation of which into the plans and programs of teachers' trainings that would improve them in the three areas: knowledge, practices, and attributes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this research study, researcher had ethical considerations by taking appropriate steps. The research took formal permission from the school regarding undertaking data collection and adhered to the ethical form provided by the school. Moreover, researcher took formal permission and approval of respondents for taking part in this collection activity and no force or compulsion was posted on any respondent for responding to the questionnaire. All participants are informed of the academic nature and anonymous nature of this study was maintained throughout so that respondents can respond with ease without any fear of implications.

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, praises and thanks to God, the Almighty, for His showers of blessings throughout in the completion and success of this study. The researchers would like to express their deep and sincere gratitude to the people who shared their invaluable time, support, and encouragement that made the completion of this research possible. The researchers extend their deepest thanks to all the science teachers and students who actively responding and participating in the study. The researchers would also like to express immeasurable thanks to their family for their love, understanding, support and valuable prayers.

REFERENCES

- Ansari, U. & Malik, S.K. (2013). Image of a Teacher in a 21st Century Classroom. *Journal of Educational and Instructional Studies in the World*, 3(4), 1-3.
- Liakopoulou, M. (2011). The Professional Competence of Teachers: Which qualities, attitudes, skills and knowledge contribute to a teacher's effectiveness? *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Makedonomaxon, Greece, 1(21), 1-13.

- Meijer, P.C., Verloop, N. & Beijaard, D. (2001). Similarities and differences in teachers' practical knowledge about teaching reading comprehension. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 94(3), 171-184.
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A Framework for Teacher Knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017.
- Murray, J. (2021). Good teachers are always learning. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 29(3), 229-235.
- Peng, W.J., Meness, E., Thomas, S., Wu, X.R., Zhang, C., Li, J.Z., & Tian, H.S. (2014). Emerging perceptions of teacher quality and teacher development in China. Elsevier, *International Journal of Educational development*, 34, 77-89.
- Rubio, C. M. (2009). Effective teachers—Professional and Personal skills. *ENSAYOS: Revista de la Facultad de Educación de Albacete*, 24, 35-46.
- Sahin, A., & Adiguzel, T. (2014). Effective Teachers Qualities from International Teachers' Perspectives. Research Gate.
- SEI-DOST & UP NISMED, (2011). Framework for Philippine Science Teacher Education. Manila: SEI-DOST & UP NISMED.
- UP NISMED-DOST-DepED (2010). Science Curriculum Framework for Basic Education. DOST. Taguig, Metro Manila.
-